

On Variation of the Transference Number of an Ion of a Strong Electrolyte in Solution according to Cube-root of its Concentration

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In previous publications it has been shown on the basis of theoretical consideration that kappa of the Debye-Hückel theory of strong electrolytes requires modification. The expression for the modified kappa, κ_m , deduced theoretically, includes within it 'the effective ionic diameter' a and varies according to cube-root of concentration of the electrolyte in solution so long as a (the effective ionic diameter) remains constant. Equations for the cationic transference numbers of the strong electrolytes deduced by using the modified κ_m have been subjected to test using the data available in the literature and have been found satisfactory.

In papers¹⁻³ published previously it has been pointed out that the expression for kappa of the Debye-Hückel theory⁴ of the strong electrolytes should be modified and the modified kappa, denoted by κ_m , is to be expressed as

$$\kappa_m = \left[\frac{2e^2}{DkT\alpha} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\frac{\sum \nu_i Z_i^2}{\nu} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\frac{\nu N}{1000} \right]^{1/3} (C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}) \quad (1)$$

$$= (B/\sqrt{a})(C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}) \quad (1a)$$

In equation (1) e , D , k , T and N have their usual significance, α represents the 'effective ionic diameter', ν_i the number of ions of the species i of the electrolyte yielding ν ions per molecule, Z_i the valency of the i ions and C_0 represents that concentration of the electrolyte at which κ_m becomes zero. In equation (1a) B represents the product of the constants in equation (1).

Using this κ_m , equations have been deduced in previous publications which can account satisfactorily for the variation of the mean activity coefficient of the ions¹⁻³ of the strong electrolytes, their molecular conductance^{2,3}, their viscosity⁵ and their apparent molal volume⁶ with dilution.

In this paper, deduction of equations, using this modified κ_m , for the transference numbers of the ions of the strong electrolytes, composed of only two kinds of ions, has been discussed.

In previous publications^{2,3} the following expression for the equivalent conductance of a strong electrolyte in solution has been deduced.

$$\lambda = \lambda_g - (A_1\lambda_0 + B_2)\kappa_m \quad (1)$$

$$= \lambda_g - (A_1\lambda_0 + B_2)(B/\sqrt{a})C^{1/3} \quad (1a)$$

where, $\lambda_g = \lambda_0 + (A_1\lambda_0 + B_2)(B/\sqrt{a})C_0^{1/3}$ and A_1 , B_2 , B are constants consisting of the universal constants

and can be calculated, C_0 represents the concentration at which κ_m is zero. λ_0 has its usual significance and a the 'effective ionic diameter' expressed in Ångström unit. The aforesaid equation (1a) after substituting the values of the constants A_1 , B_2 and B simplifying may be written as

$$\lambda = \lambda_g - S \left[\frac{1.22}{\sqrt{a}} \right] C^{1/3} \quad (1b)$$

where at 25°, $S = (0.23\lambda_0 + 60.19)$ for a 1 : 1 electrolyte³. Equation (1b) may also be written as

$$(\lambda_+) + (\lambda_-) = (\lambda_{g+}) + (\lambda_{g-}) - S(1.22/\sqrt{a})C^{1/3} \quad (1c)$$

where, λ_+ and λ_- represent the equivalent conductance of the positive and the negative ions respectively and λ_{g+} and λ_{g-} the corresponding quantities at infinite dilution. It is to be noted that

$$[(\lambda_+) + (\lambda_-)] = \lambda \text{ and } [(\lambda_{g+}) + (\lambda_{g-})] = \lambda_g$$

The expressions for the equivalent conductance of the individual ions can be found from equation (1c) by splitting it up in the following way,

$$\lambda_+ = \lambda_{g+} - i S(1.22/\sqrt{a})C^{1/3} \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda_- = \lambda_{g-} - (1-i) S(1.22/\sqrt{a})C^{1/3} \quad (2a)$$

where, i is a constant.

Equation (2) leads to the expression for the transference number of the cations as

$$T_+ = \frac{\lambda_+}{(\lambda_+) + (\lambda_-)} = \frac{\lambda_+ - \lambda_{g+} - i S(1.22/\sqrt{a})C^{1/3}}{\lambda_+ - \lambda_{g+} - i S(1.22/\sqrt{a})C^{1/3} + \lambda_{g-} - (1-i) S(1.22/\sqrt{a})C^{1/3}}$$

$$= \frac{[(\lambda_{g+}) - i S(1.22/\sqrt{a})C^{1/3}]}{\lambda_g}$$

$$= T_+^0 - (S/\lambda_g)(1.22/\sqrt{a})[i - T_+^0]C^{1/3} \quad (2b)$$

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neglecting terms involving $C^{2/3}$, such as $i(S/\lambda_g)^2 (1.22/\sqrt{a})^2 C^{2/3}$ and its higher powers.

Similarly, the expression for the transference number of the anion may be written as

$$T_- = T_-^0 - (S/\lambda_g)(1.22/\sqrt{a})[1 - i - T_+^0]C^{1/3} \quad (2c)$$

The constants $(i - T_+^0)$ and \sqrt{a} in equation (2b) may be put together and it may be expressed as

$$T_+ = T_+^0 - (S/\lambda_g)(1.22)[(i - T_+^0)/\sqrt{a}]C^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

$$= T_+^0 - S_m(C)^{1/3} \quad (3a)$$

where, $S_m = (S/\lambda_g)(1.22)[(i - T_+^0)/\sqrt{a}]$

A plot of T_+ against $C^{1/3}$ has been found to be linear.

From the slope and intercept of the straight line, S_m and T_+^0 can be found. λ_g and \sqrt{a} in equation (3) can be found from data on measurements of equivalent conductance of the electrolyte available in the literature, but i and T^0 are to be found from data on measurements of cationic transference number. Attention may also be drawn to the fact that $(i - T_+^0)/\sqrt{a}$ is a characteristic constant of the electrolyte used and it may be related to such other fundamental property of the electrolyte as the sum of its ionic radii r_- and r_+ . It has been found that for the 1:1 electrolytes containing a common anion, such as the Cl^- ion, the following equation holds good

$$(i - T_+^0)/\sqrt{a} = -m(r_- + r_+) + m_0 \quad (4)$$

where, m and m_0 are constants.

The Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation⁸ for the transference number of the cation of a strong electrolyte is expressed as

$$T = T_+^0 + S_{(T_+)}C^{1/2} \quad (L)$$

where, $S_{(T_+)} = \left[\frac{T_+^0(Z_- + Z_+) - Z_+}{(Z_- + Z_+)\lambda_0} \right] B_2$ (La)

In equation (La), Z_- and Z_+ denote the valency of the cation and the anion respectively of the electrolyte used, and B_2 has the same significance as stated already.

The equations (3a) and (L) have been subjected to comparative test using such data as are available in the literature and are recommended for their precision.

Processing of the data and verification of the equations :

The data recorded in the Tables 1 and 2 have been collected from the literature⁹. Under the head miscellaneous of the Tables are mentioned the electrolyte, the equation used and the values of the constants in the equation. C represents molar concentration and the other terms have their usual significance. The values of T_+^0 and S_m in equation (3a) have been found from plots of T_+ against $C^{1/3}$ as stated already. It is to be noted that S_m is positive or negative according as T_+^0 is less or greater than i . In Table 3 are recorded the data used for verifying equation (4).

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF T_+ WITH CONCENTRATION FOR 1:1 ELECTROLYTES AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	Values of T_+ (cationic transport number)		
		Observed	Calcd. Eqn. (3a)	Calcd. Eqn. (L)
HCl Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.8199$ $S_m = -0.0246$	0.01	0.825 1	0.825 2	0.825 4
	0.02	0.826 6	0.826 6	0.827 3
	0.05	0.829 2	0.829 0	0.831 0
Eqn. (L) $T_+^0 = 0.8209$ $S_{(T_+)} = +0.04507$	0.1	0.831 4	0.831 3	0.835 2
	0.01	0.328 9	0.329 0	0.327 9
	0.02	0.326 1	0.325 9	0.324 4
LiCl Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.3388$ $S_m = 0.0475$	0.05	0.321 1	0.321 3	0.317 5
	0.1	0.316 8	0.316 8	0.310 4
	0.01	0.391 8	0.391 7	0.391 4
NaCl Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.3971$ $S_m = 0.0252$	0.02	0.390 2	0.390 3	0.389 4
	0.05	0.387 6	0.387 8	0.385 3
	0.10	0.385 4	0.385 4	0.380 8
Eqn. (L) $T_+^0 = 0.3963$ $S_{(T_+)} = -0.04910$	0.01	0.490 2	0.490 2	0.490 2
	0.02	0.490 1	0.490 1	0.490 1
	0.05	0.489 9	0.489 9	0.489 8
KCl Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.4906$ $S_m = 0.00185$	0.05	0.489 9	0.489 9	0.489 8
	0.1	0.489 8	0.489 7	0.489 4
	0.2	0.489 4	0.489 5	0.488 9
Eqn. (L) $T_+^0 = 0.4906$ $S_{(T_+)} = -0.00376$	0.01	0.490 7	0.490 7	0.490 5
	0.02	0.490 6	0.490 6	0.490 4
	0.05	0.490 5	0.490 5	0.490 1
NH ₄ Cl Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.4910$ $S_m = 0.00135$	0.05	0.490 7	0.490 7	0.489 8
	0.1	0.490 7	0.490 4	0.489 8
	0.01	0.508 4	0.508 3	0.507 2
KNO ₃ Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.5072$ $S_m = -0.0065$	0.02	0.508 7	0.508 7	0.507 3
	0.05	0.509 3	0.509 3	0.507 6
	0.1	0.510 3	0.509 9	0.507 3
Eqn. (L) $T_+^0 = 0.5069$ $S_{(T_+)} = +0.00297$	0.01	0.464 8	0.464 8	0.462 7
	0.02	0.465 2	0.465 4	0.462 0
	0.05	0.466 4	0.466 4	0.460 7
AgNO ₃ Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.4627$ $S_m = -0.01$	0.05	0.466 4	0.466 4	0.460 7
	0.1	0.468 2	0.467 4	0.459 2
	0.01	0.558 7	0.558 8	0.554 0
CH ₃ COONa Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.5489$ $S_m = -0.0226$	0.02	0.555 0	0.555 0	0.555 4
	0.05	0.557 3	0.557 3	0.558 2
	0.1	0.559 4	0.559 4	0.561 3
Eqn. (L) $T_+^0 = 0.5507$ $S_{(T_+)} = +0.03336$	0.01	0.649 8	0.650 0	0.650 2
	0.02	0.652 3	0.652 4	0.653 2
	0.05	0.656 9	0.656 7	0.659 4
CH ₃ COOK Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.6405$ $S_m = -0.044$	0.1	0.660 9	0.660 9	0.666 3
	0.01	0.642 7	0.642 7	0.642 7
	0.05	0.642 7	0.642 7	0.642 7
Eqn. (L) $T_+^0 = 0.6427$ $S_{(T_+)} = +0.07467$	0.01	0.642 7	0.642 7	0.642 7

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF T_+ WITH CONCENTRATION FOR 2:1 AND 3:1 ELECTROLYTES AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	Values of T_+ (cation transport number)		
		Observed	Calcd. Eqn. (3a)	Calcd. Eqn. (L)
K ₂ SO ₄ Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.4780$ $S_m = -0.0301$	0.005	0.482 9	0.483 1	0.486 4
	0.01	0.484 8	0.484 5	0.489 4
	0.025	0.487 0	0.486 8	0.493 8
Eqn. (L) $T_+^0 = 0.4790$ $S_{(T_+)} = +0.1048$	0.05	0.489 0	0.489 1	0.502 4
	0.005	0.426 4	0.426 4	0.424 9
	0.01	0.422 0	0.421 8	0.419 5
CaCl ₂ Eqn. (3a) $T_+^0 = 0.4438$ $S_m = 0.102$	0.025	0.414 0	0.414 0	0.411 9
	0.01	0.426 4	0.426 4	0.424 9
	0.025	0.414 0	0.414 0	0.411 9
Eqn. (L) $T_+^0 = 0.4380$ $S_{(T_+)} = -0.2614$	0.05	0.406 0	0.406 2	0.396 6

(Table 2 contd.)

LaCl ₃	0.003 33	0.462 5	0.463 2	0.458 7
Eqn. (3a), T ₊ ⁰ =	0.485 2	0.006 67	0.457 6	0.457 3
S _m =	0.148			
Eqn. (L), T ₊ ⁰ =	0.477 0	0.016 7	0.448 2	0.447 4
S(T ₊)=	-0.317 0	0.033 3	0.437 5	0.437 5
				0.419 0

results better than equation (L). In the combined constant $(i - T_+^0) / \sqrt{a}$, T_+^0 depends on the equivalent conductances λ_{g+} and λ_{g-} of the cations and anions respectively at infinite dilution. Since λ_{g+} , λ_{g-} and a , are all dependent on the size of the ions, so it is assumed that they may be related to the crystallo-

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF $(i - T_+^0) / \sqrt{a}$ WITH $(r_- + r_+)^{1/2}$ OF THE CHLORIDES OF 1 : 1 ELECTROLYTES AT 25°

Constants in eqn. (4)	Electrolyte	$(r_- + r_+)^{1/2}$	(1.22)S	λ_g	S _m	Values of $(i - T_+^0) / \sqrt{a}$	
						Observed	Calcd. eqn. (4)
m=0.247	LiCl	1.55	0.919	115.03	0.047 5	0.052	0.054
	NaCl	1.66	0.861	126.43	0.025 2	0.029	0.027
	KCl	1.77	0.771	149.86	0.001 85	0.002 4	0.002
m ₀ =0.437	NH ₄ Cl	1.77	0.490	149.94	0.001 85	0.001 8	0.002
	HCl	1.98	0.453	426.17	-0.024 6	-0.054	-0.051

Discussion

Attention may be drawn to the fact that the values of λ_+ and λ_- the constituent ions of an electrolyte depend not only on interionic attraction but also on hydration which determines the size of the ions. At infinite dilution interionic attraction vanishes but the effect of hydration persists. The data presented in the Tables 1 and 2 involve the assumption that hydration remains constant in the concentration range 0.01 to 0.1 N. If, however, the hydration of the ions decreases as the concentration of the electrolyte increases to 0.1 N or to a still higher value, then a , in equation (3a) would decrease producing disagreement between the observed and the calculated values of T_+ .

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that for the 1 : 1 electrolytes the values of T_+ calculated by using equation (3a) agree with the observed ones better than those calculated by using the Onsager equation (L). For AgNO₃ the slope observed is positive while that calculated by using Onsager equation (La) is negative. For this electrolyte it may also be noted that the value of T_+ at 0.1 N, calculated by equation (3a) is lower than that observed. Although it is still within the limits of experimental error yet it may be taken as an indication that hydration of the Ag⁺ ion is tending to decrease. The NO₃ ion which is believed to be a strong 'structure breaker' may be responsible for this effect.

The data for the unsymmetrical electrolytes, recorded in Table 2, confirm the conclusion drawn already that equation (3a) fits the experimental

graphic radii r_+ and r_- of these ions of an electrolyte. An attempt was, therefore, made to correlate them and it was found that an equation of the following type holds good for the chlorides of the 1 : 1 electrolytes,

$$(i - T_+^0) / \sqrt{a} = -m(r_- + r_+)^{1/2} + m_0 \tag{4}$$

where, $m=0.247$ and $m_0=0.437$.

It will be noticed from the data, recorded in Table 3, for the chlorides of the 1 : 1 electrolyte, that the calculated values of $(i - T_+^0) / \sqrt{a}$ agree well with those observed. The value of $(r_- + r_+)$ of NH₄Cl has been taken to be the same as that of KCl. It follows from equation (4) that $i = T_+^0 - \sqrt{a} [m(r_- + r_+)^{1/2} - m_0]$.

For 1 : 1 electrolytes having a common anion other than the chloride it is worthwhile investigating whether an equation similar to (4) holds good or not.

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